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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE**

**14. Management Approaches to Ensuring
National Security: Legal and Organizational
Challenges. By ANDRII STRETOVYCH. and
others. p. 272.**

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**MANAGEMENT APPROACHES TO ENSURING
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ABSTRACT

The aim is to develop an integrated model of public administration of national security that combines organizational and legal mechanisms, information resources and human resources to improve the effectiveness of strategic planning. The research is based on systemic, institutional, subjective and objective approaches, including content analysis of strategic documents, stakeholder analysis, multi-criteria risk assessment and modeling of management scenarios to analyze the interaction of legal, information and personnel components. A model of public administration has been developed that integrates legal, institutional and instrumental subsystems, performance indicators have been identified, the need for coordination between levels of government has been proved, and tools for evaluating management mechanisms have been proposed, which contributes to the sustainability of national security. Further research can be aimed at detailing the mechanisms of interagency cooperation, improving information and analytical systems for threat forecasting, and developing training programs for personnel with due regard to regional peculiarities and new global challenges.

Keywords: *public administration, national security, organizational and legal factors, information policy, human resources, strategic planning*

1- INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, characterized by dynamic transformations of the geopolitical order, volatility of financial markets and an increasing number of hybrid threats, ensuring national security is one of the priority tasks of public administration. At the same time, none of the components of national security, whether economic, political, military, social or informational, can be considered in isolation from the others, as they are all closely interconnected. In particular, it is the level of national security that largely determines the effectiveness of the state's overall functioning, as well as the ability of government institutions to respond in a timely manner to internal and external challenges¹.

However, the inverse relationship is no less important: aggravation of threats in other areas, such as information aggression, personnel degradation of the administrative apparatus or organizational destruction of security institutions, can significantly affect the financial stability of the state, necessitating the redistribution of resources, increased spending on defense, security, cyber defense, etc. In this context, there is a need for a comprehensive study of organizational, legal, informational and personnel elements as the main ones for the public administration system of national security capable of

¹ McCaffrey, C., & Poitiers, N. F. (2024). *Instruments of economic security* (Bruegel Working Paper 12/2024). Bruegel. https://www.bruegel.org/system/files/2024-05/WP%2012%202024_0.pdf

functioning in the context of multi-vector threat dynamics. Understanding the interdependence between the individual elements of national security allows identifying the most vulnerable links in the public administration system, formulating effective management decisions to prevent potential crises, and building resilience strategies aimed at ensuring the stability of the country's functioning in both the short and long term². Of particular importance in this process is the issue of staffing of public authorities, the level of legal regulation of management processes, as well as the effectiveness of information support for national security activities³.

The study of public-administrative aspects of national security through the prism of organizational, legal, informational and personnel factors is extremely relevant, since these components form the basis of the state's managerial capacity to achieve national interests, counter threats and strengthen the security architecture in the face of new global and regional challenges.

Literature Review

According to Wiśniewski⁴, national security is seen as a complex state that depends on the interaction of various areas of public administration, where a special place is occupied by organizational and legal mechanisms aimed at countering threats and ensuring the stability of the country's key systems. Globalization, according to the author's observations, increases the impact of external factors on national security, which requires improvement of information and human resources for effective response to challenges. In the same vein, Ahmed⁵ and Slawotsky⁶ emphasize that national security is formed through the coordinated activities of the branches of government that ensure the protection of national interests in such areas as the organization of management processes, legal regulation and staffing, which allows the state to withstand both internal and external destabilizing factors.

Researchers point out the importance of a systematic approach to the analysis of national security, considering it as a set of interrelated elements, among which Jaźwiński⁷ identifies organizational and legal framework, information stability and human resources, which together create the basis for the effective functioning of the state. This approach allows assessing the state of the country's security through the

² Mura, L., Daňová, M., Vavrek, R., & Dúbravská, M. (2017). Economic freedom – Classification of its level and impact on the economic security. *AD ALTA: Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 7(2), 154–157. http://www.magnanimitas.cz/ADALTA/0702/papers/A_mura.pdf

³ Koch, M. (2022). Social policy without growth: Moving towards sustainable welfare states. *Social Policy and Society*, 21(3), 447–459. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1474746421000361>

⁴ Wiśniewski, R. (2018). Notion of strategic national security management. *Security and Defense Quarterly*, 20(3), 18–41. <https://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0012.4887>

⁵ Ahmed, A. (2024, May 19). Book review: *Hidden in plain sight: Redefining the field of national security* (Reviewing *Race and National Security*, M. Sirleaf (Ed.), Oxford Univ. Press, 2023). *The Harvard National Security Journal*, 15. <https://harvardnsj.org/2024/05/19/book-review-hidden-in-plain-sight-redefining-the-field-of-national-security-reviewing-race-and-national-security-matiangai-sirleaf-ed-oxford-univ-press-2023/>

⁶ Slawotsky, J. (2024, October 11). Conceptualizing national security in an era of great power rivalry: Implications for international economic law. *East Asia*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12140-024-09434-y>

⁷ Jaźwiński, I. (2023). Economic security threats. Determinants of state functioning and economic policy. *Strategic Review*, 16), 77–88. <https://doi.org/10.14746/ps.2023.1.6>

ability of governance structures to prevent threats, adapt legislation to new challenges, and provide sufficient training to implement security strategies. At the same time, Mumtaz et al.⁸ focus on the need to take into account micro aspects, in particular training at the level of individual institutions that ensure the stability of management processes and promote national security through the proper performance of duties.

The institutional approach to national security proposed by Adhikari⁹, Makedon et al.¹⁰ emphasizes the crucial role of state bodies in creating conditions for the stable development of the country, emphasizing their ability to maintain information security, reduce the impact of external threats and prevent conflicts within power structures over the allocation of resources. Such a statement implies that the effectiveness of governance depends on the quality of organizational and legal mechanisms that regulate the activities of institutions, as well as on the level of professional training of personnel who implement these mechanisms in practice.

According to Lantis¹¹, Oerlemans and Langenhuijzen¹², national security is defined as a state where the state has sufficient resources to meet public needs and fulfill its obligations, which is achieved through a well-established organizational structure, clear legal regulation and effective use of information technology to protect the interests of citizens and the state. These facts emphasize the importance of reconciling the interests of different governance actors to reduce internal contradictions, which requires the creation of appropriate mechanisms for coordination and professional development of personnel involved in the security process. Instead, Ryabets¹³, Urych and Matyasik¹⁴ focus on the issue of balanced management systems, noting that national security depends on the harmonious development of organizational, legal and informational components, which together create conditions for the country's social and economic progress.

Some authors, such as Shayana and Rufus¹⁵, focus on the state-centered approach, considering national security as the protection of state interests through the stability of management processes, legal certainty and personnel readiness to perform strategic

⁸ Mumtaz, Z., Enworo, O. C., & Mokomane, Z. (2024, April 25). A case for the inclusion of informal social protection in social policy theory and practice: Lessons from Nigeria and Pakistan. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00219096241249975>

⁹ Adhikari, L. D. (2024). Exploring the relationship between national security risks and economic factors: A Nepalese perspective. *Journal of Political Science*, 24(1), 39–56. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jps.v24i1.62853>

¹⁰ Makedon, V., Trachova, D., Myronchuk, V., Opalchuk, R., & Davydenko, O. (2024). The development and characteristics of sustainable finance. In A. Hamdan (Ed.), *Achieving sustainable business through AI, technology education and computer science* (Vol. 163, pp. 373–382). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-73632-2_31

¹¹ Lantis, J. S. (2002). Strategic culture and national security policy. *International Studies Review*, 4(3), 87–113. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1521-9488.t01-1-00266>

¹² Oerlemans, J.-J., & Langenhuijzen, S. (2024, September 12). Balancing national security and privacy: Examining the use of commercially available information in OSINT practices. *International Journal of Intelligence and Counter Intelligence*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08850607.2024.2387850>

¹³ Ryabets, K. (2023). Legality and rule of law as principles of public administration. *Scientific Bulletin: Public Administration*, 1(13), 70–85. [https://doi.org/10.33269/2618-0065-2023-1\(13\)-70-85](https://doi.org/10.33269/2618-0065-2023-1(13)-70-85)

¹⁴ Urych, I., & Matyasik, G. (2022). Preparing youth for defense: Socialization, education, and training of young people in Europe for national security. *Security and Defense Quarterly*, 38(2), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.35467/sdq/149891>

¹⁵ Shayana, T. K., & Rufus, D. (2024). Safeguarding national security: Combating terrorism and ensuring good governance. *Journal of Advance Research in Science and Social Science*, 7(1). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/383670545_Safeguarding_National_Security_Combating_Terrorism_and_Ensuring_Good_Governance

tasks. This view is justified if we consider the state as the main actor coordinating efforts to protect society, but it needs to be clarified in terms of the interaction between different levels of government and the role of information systems in this process.

Mahmutovic and Alhamoudi¹⁶, Tymoshenko¹⁷ propose a dynamic approach, in which national security is seen as a process that includes monitoring threats, analyzing stability indicators and active state risk management, where organizational structures, legal norms and training are key to responding to challenges in a timely manner. Anderson¹⁸ interprets national security as a multilayered system consisting of subsystems such as organizational, legal, information and personnel, each of which has its own structure and dynamics, but together they ensure the integrity and sustainability of the state. Similarly, the RAND Europe report¹⁹ emphasizes the formation of a multi-level national security system, where organizational mechanisms, legal framework, and information and human resources interact to counter threats at different levels of government. Researchers agree that effective public administration in this area requires further development of comprehensive research that will take into account both institutional and subjective aspects, as well as adaptation to modern conditions that are constantly changing under the influence of global and domestic factors.

The purpose of the study is to provide a comprehensive justification for the development of the public-management mechanism of the national security of the country in terms of organizational, legal, information and personnel components.

Research methodology

The methodological basis of the study is based on four key approaches: systemic, institutional, subjective and objective, which together form a holistic analytical model for studying public administration mechanisms in the field of national security. Firstly, the systemic approach allows covering a wide range of factors affecting the stability of management structures, information infrastructure and personnel policy in the context of ensuring the security of the State, considering them not in isolation, but as elements of a single functional complex.

Secondly, the institutional approach is focused on studying the organizational architecture of public administration in the field of national security, in particular, the efficiency of state bodies, their ability to adapt in crisis conditions, the level of regulatory support, and mechanisms of interagency coordination. This approach makes it possible to assess the real institutional capacity of the state to perform security functions, to identify systemic deficiencies in personnel management and legal regulation.

¹⁶ Mahmutovic, A., & Alhamoudi, A. (2023). Understanding the relationship between the rule of law and sustainable development. *Access to Justice in Eastern Europe*, 7(1), 170–197. <https://doi.org/10.33327/AJEE-18-7.1-a000102>

¹⁷ Tymoshenko, V. I. (2024). Internal threats to the national security of Ukraine. *Analytical and Comparative Jurisprudence*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.24144/2788-6018.2024.02.14>

¹⁸ Anderson, D. (2024). National security and human rights. *European Convention Human Rights Law Review*, 2/2025. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5037694>

¹⁹ RAND Europe. (2024). *Relationships between the economy and national security*. Research and Documentation Center (WODC). https://www.rand.org/content/dam/rand/pubs/research_reports/RR4200/RR4287/RAND_RR4287.pdf

Thirdly, the application of the subjective approach allows to focus on the interaction of the main actors of public administration: state bodies, non-governmental institutions, local self-government bodies, expert community and civil society in the process of formulating national security policies. This approach is aimed at identifying mechanisms for balancing the interests of key actors, preventing abuse of power, improving transparency and accountability procedures, and increasing trust in security institutions. Finally, the object-based approach involves the study of specific elements of public administration as objects that are targeted by management interventions. In this context, the level of sustainability of the legal, human resources and information subsystems of the national security system, their ability to function effectively in conditions of high risk dynamics is analyzed.

2. RESULTS

2.1. INSTITUTIONAL AND LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN THE FIELD OF NATIONAL SECURITY

2.1.1. STRUCTURE AND FUNCTIONAL SUBSYSTEMS OF THE STATE ADMINISTRATION OF NATIONAL SECURITY

In the structure of the modern state policy in the field of national security of Ukraine, one of the key areas is the formation of an effective public administration mechanism that covers organizational, legal, informational and personnel factors, which together determine the ability of the state to respond in a timely manner to current threats, ensure the stability of the management system and guarantee the protection of the strategic interests of the state²⁰. Within this approach, the state management of security processes becomes institutionally structured, based on the operation of legal norms, coordinated work of institutions and the use of effective management tools.

Given the importance of public administration as an integrative platform for the implementation of the state policy in the field of national security, we can distinguish three main interrelated subsystems that ensure the functioning of the relevant management mechanism, namely: legal, institutional and instrumental. Each of these subsystems performs a separate, but at the same time inextricably linked function in the system of ensuring stable, predictable and effective functioning of public authorities and the security sector in general (Figure 1).

The legal subsystem is a set of legal acts, legislative initiatives and regulatory procedures that create a legal framework for the activities of state institutions in the field of national security, in particular, the regulation of risk management procedures, the responsibility of officials, the procedure for the application of emergency security measures and the coordination of interagency cooperation. This subsystem forms the

²⁰ Korostashyets, Yu. (2024). The rule of law is the fundamental principle of private procedural legal relations. *Expert: Paradigm of Law and Public Administration*, 4(32), 25–30. [https://doi.org/10.32689/2617-9660-2024-4\(32\)-25-30](https://doi.org/10.32689/2617-9660-2024-4(32)-25-30)

framework conditions within which public authorities exercise their powers, in particular in terms of personnel policy, information transparency and legal support for the stability of management decisions²¹.

Figure 1. Integral subsystems that form the national security contour in the context of public administration development

Source: created by the author

2.1.2. INTEGRATION OF ORGANIZATIONAL, INFORMATION AND HUMAN RESOURCES INTO THE SECURITY SYSTEM

The institutional subsystem covers the system of specialized state bodies, institutions and structures that manage, monitor, analyze and respond to threats to national security, including both military and civilian elements of public administration. The instrumental subsystem is a set of practical management mechanisms, methodologies, analytical procedures and technological solutions aimed at the efficient use of available resources (information, personnel, organizational) in the process of ensuring national security. It includes threat assessment algorithms, risk management models, digital information and analytical security management systems, as well as specific management actions to monitor, forecast and adapt security strategies based on up-to-date information. It is this subsystem that allows transforming legislative regulations and institutional decisions into practical actions, ensuring prompt response to dynamic threats and the formation of flexible management scenarios (Figure 2).

Therefore, effective public administration in the field of national security should include not only high-quality interaction between financial and security institutions, but also strategic planning of resources, human resources, legal regulation and information support for the state's actions in crisis or unusual situations²².

²¹ Khadzhiradieva, S., Bezverkhniuk, T., Nazarenko, O., Bazyka, S., & Dotsenko, T. (2024). Personal data protection: Between human rights protection and national security. *Social & Legal Studies*, 7(3), 245–256. <https://doi.org/10.32518/sals3.2024.245>

²² Han, R. (2018). Financial internationalization and financial security issues. *Open Access Library Journal*, 5, e4874, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1104874>

The institutional capacity to quickly adapt to new challenges, while ensuring transparency, accountability and efficiency, is a determining factor in the stability of both financial and public security²³. That is why the integration of organizational, legal, informational and personnel components in the public administration system should become a priority of the state policy in the field of national security, focused on preventing threats and minimizing systemic risks (Figure 3).

The system of state public administration of national security faces a number of complex and multifaceted challenges, which are manifested in the discrepancy between the ambitious tasks of socio-economic development and the actual capabilities of the regions, in the lack of readiness of human resources to implement innovative approaches, in the discrepancies between national and local management strategies, as well as in internal conflicts of interest between different groups of actors involved in these processes²⁴.

²³ Delalibera, B. R., Ferreira, P. C., & Parente, R. M. (2025). *Social security reforms, retirement and sectoral decisions* (International Monetary Fund Working Paper No. 2025/032). <https://doi.org/10.5089/9798229000222.001>

²⁴ Makedon, V. V., Valikov, V. P., & Koshlyak, Ye. Ye. (2020). The global labor market in the coordinates of the digital economy. *Academic Review*, (1(52)), 91–104. <https://doi.org/10.32342/2074-5354-2020-1-52-9>

Figure 2. Basic components of public administration of national security

Source: created by the author

Figure 3. The institutional field of national security and the formation of interconnections between its components

Source: created by the author

The model of implementation of the strategic goals of the national security of Ukraine, designed with a perspective until 2030, aimed at achieving sustainable development in accordance with national priorities, provides for close interaction of key public administration entities within the framework of state policy, which is possible only if strategic documents at the national level are harmonized with regional development plans, as well as their continuous improvement, taking into account the specifics of various management structures. The effectiveness of this model depends on clearly defined organizational and legal mechanisms, the use of modern information systems to coordinate actions and improve the level of training of personnel capable of ensuring the fulfillment of tasks in the context of dynamic challenges facing the state²⁵.

Despite the diversity of their approaches to national security analysis, researchers often use the verbal-logical method to identify key indicators, which, however, focuses mainly on assessing general trends and rates of socio-economic development of regions, rather than on a detailed study of the actors that shape security interests or specific

²⁵ De Becker, E. (2023). The Role of Social Security in the Combat of In-work Poverty. In L. Ratti & P. Schoukens (Eds.), *Working yet poor: Challenges to EU social citizenship* (pp. 139–186). Hart Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781509966578.ch-007>

sources of threats, which requires additional deepening of analytical methods. In this regard, there is a need to conduct a reverse analysis that would allow comparing regional development strategies with the provisions of the National Security Strategy until 2030, using content analysis of strategic planning documents to assess their compliance with national goals, as well as checking the availability of the organizational and legal framework, information resources and staffing to implement these strategies, which will help identify weaknesses and formulate proposals to address them²⁶.

The key indicators characterizing the public component of national security within the framework of the relevant strategic approach include a number of indicators reflecting the state and dynamics of various spheres of economic and social life of the country. In particular, this includes macroeconomic indicators of the real sector of the economy, which allow assessing the overall efficiency and stability of economic activity; indicators of scientific and technical security, which serve to analyze the innovative potential and level of technological development of the territory; as well as indicators of personnel and information security. The schematic representation presented in Figure 4 a model for the formation and achievement of strategic goals of Ukraine's national security is proposed, which will ensure the harmonization of interests at the macro, meso and micro levels, which is a key aspect of public administration. The proposed model is characterized by a hierarchical approach, where the priority of the macro level of national security determines the leading role of strategic documents developed and approved at the national level, which allows creating an integrated system of public administration aimed at improving the financial stability and security of the state.

One of the key problems in the field of practical public administration of the national security of the state is the absence of a clearly defined public administration entity responsible for achieving the strategic goals set forth in the relevant programs and concepts. This issue has been repeatedly raised by critics of strategic documents related

²⁶ Metelenko, N., Kovalenko, O., Makedon, V., Merzhynskyi, Y., & Rudych, A. (2019). Infrastructure security of formation and development of sectoral corporate clusters. *Journal of Security and Sustainability Issues*, 9(1), 77–89. <https://scispace.com/pdf/infrastructure-security-of-formation-and-development-of-zwob9gce4q.pdf>

to national security, and it remains one of the main reasons why most decisions in this area are mostly theoretical and not always implemented in practice. In this regard, it is of particular importance to develop effective mechanisms for harmonizing the interests of state public administration and local self-government bodies, which will contribute to a more efficient functioning of the national security system at different levels of public administration.

Figure 4. The mechanism of public administration of national security in the system of potential threats

Source: created by the author

2.2. STRATEGIC PLANNING AND TOOLS FOR ENSURING NATIONAL SECURITY

2.2.1. APPLICATION OF STRATEGIC PLANNING IN PUBLIC SECURITY MANAGEMENT

The strategy of comprehensive national security planning at different levels of public administration is of critical importance. One of the key tools in the process of

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comprehensive planning and ensuring national national security is an inventory of material and financial resources with the obligatory allocation of the meso-level, which will ensure proper control by regional and local authorities over the effective use of the available resource potential, as well as facilitate the assessment of the environmental situation and other important parameters that have a significant impact on financial security. To achieve a balance between the interests of state, local authorities and business, it is necessary to improve the system of contractual relations and expand public partnership mechanisms, which will help to establish effective cooperation at all levels of public administration and create favorable conditions for the long-term development of public administration²⁷.

However, in the process of public administration of national security, certain contradictions arise between the interests of state public administration, local self-government and business entities, which complicates the implementation of strategic programs. In view of this, the stakeholder analysis approach should be used in management practice, which became popular after the publication of R. Freeman’s works and proved to be effective in strategic planning processes. The main idea of this approach is to use technologies that allow not only to identify key groups of stakeholders – representatives of business, government agencies, and the public – but also to assess their impact on achieving strategic development goals. Accordingly, the application of this approach contributes to a more accurate determination of the priorities of the state policy in the field of national security and the development of effective models for its provision, taking into account the specific interests of different stakeholders (Table 1).

Table 1. Tools and models of the stakeholder approach in the system of public administration of national security of Ukraine

Tools and models of the stakeholder approach	Description of the method
Stakeholder map	A tool that reflects the subjective vision of the leadership of a public authority or a management team, formed, for example, through the brainstorming technique, of which entities may be involved in the implementation of national security strategies, whose interests may be affected in the process of their implementation, and how these interests affect the organizational, legal, informational and personnel aspects of ensuring the stability of the state at the national or regional levels.

²⁷ United Nations. (2024). *World Economic Situation and Prospects 2024*. https://www.un.org/development/desa/dpad/wp-content/uploads/sites/45/WESP_2024_Web.pdf

Table of stakeholder interests	A method that involves the systematization of data on key actors, their level of influence on the processes of public administration of national security, the degree of support or resistance to the proposed measures, as well as the detailing of their interests, which allows developing an interaction strategy aimed at harmonizing these interests with the tasks of improving the efficiency of organizational and legal regulation, information support and personnel policy in the context of national security of Ukraine.
Matrix “support multiplied by the power of influence”	An analytical tool that helps to identify stakeholders with high potential for influence but low level of support for national security strategies, which may pose risks to their implementation, as well as to identify those who demonstrate significant support in order to optimize cooperation with them to strengthen the organizational, legal, information and personnel components of the state security management system.
Integrated assessment of the national security environment	An approach that characterizes the risks to national security associated with the human factor, in particular the behavior of stakeholders that can destabilize management processes, and is used for a comprehensive analysis of internal and external threats in the field of public administration, taking into account organizational structures, legal norms, information flows and human resources as key elements of ensuring stability.
Multi-criteria stakeholder analysis	The methodology, which includes an assessment of the long-term effects of the implementation of national security strategies, taking into account their social significance and resource intensity, is used to analyze stakeholder interests when choosing management initiatives, forecasting possible conflicts between parties, with the assessment of the impact of projects based on expert opinions, and the search for an optimal balance between interests is achieved through multi-criteria optimization methods with a focus on organizational, legal, information, and personnel factors.

Source: created by the author

In today’s realities, the issue of harmonizing economic interests between key institutional actors involved in the implementation of large-scale mega-projects, including private business, the state and regional authorities, is becoming increasingly relevant, as these projects are not only of national importance, but also involve a large number of parties and cover several regions simultaneously. Undoubtedly, the strategic

public management of such initiatives, as well as the harmonization of interests between all involved institutional actors, should be integrated into the public administration system, which is an important element of ensuring the national security of the state, because it is at this level that the specifics of local needs and resources can be effectively taken into account²⁸.

Solving problems related to the mitigation of contradictions in conflict zones is gaining not only regional, but also national and strategic importance, as it affects the stability of economic development and financial security of the country as a whole, which emphasizes the need for an integrated approach to public administration²⁹.

Special attention should also be paid to the regional strategy of the state public administration of national security. At the meso-level, the system of state public administration of national security involves the adaptation of classical management functions to the specifics of regional development, which requires an integrated approach to their integration into strategic planning mechanisms. Given the dynamism of the modern economic environment, management functions should be flexible, adaptive and aimed at long-term financial stability in the state (Figure 5).

The use of planning procedures opens up opportunities for regions to determine their future development prospects, promotes more rational use of available regional resources, and allows for the effective implementation of policies aimed at reconciling the interests of various stakeholders, which is critical to ensuring financial stability and security at the local level.

Planning in the field of public administration is of particular importance when it comes to the development and implementation of state policy in the field of national security, as it allows, in the face of uncertainty of the future, to make timely and reasonable forecasts of the development of the situation in the political, social, economic and security dimensions both at the local and national levels, thereby laying the foundation for making decisions that have a long-term impact on the functioning of public authorities and security structures.

²⁸ Weissmann, M. (2025). Future threat landscapes: The impact on intelligence and security services. *Security and Defense Quarterly*, 49(1), 40–57. <https://doi.org/10.35467/sdq/197248>

²⁹ Vakulyk, O., Petrenko, P., Kuzmenko, I., Pochtovyi, M., & Orlovskiy, R. (2020). Cybersecurity as a Component of the National Security of the State. *Journal of Security and Sustainability Issues*, 9(3), 775–784. <https://journals.lka.lt/journal/jssi/article/660/info>

Figure 5. Processes of taking into account imbalances and directions of ensuring national security in the public administration system of Ukraine

Source: created by the author

2.2.2. METHODS OF STAKEHOLDER MANAGEMENT AND FUNCTIONAL ASPECTS OF SECURITY POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

The use of modern approaches to planning requires not only the development of detailed strategies and schedules for the implementation of specific management actions, but also the introduction of a system of clearly defined indicators that would allow for a qualitative assessment of the performance of executive bodies, analyze the progress of tasks aimed at strengthening national security, and ensure transparency in the implementation of relevant programs³⁰. In this context, it is important to integrate human resources capable not only of implementing strategies but also of adapting them to changing conditions with the help of modern information and analytical tools and legal support.

First of all, planning is preceded by the forecasting stage, which in public administration practice is a necessary tool for modeling possible scenarios of the situation, allowing to formulate alternative options for action and choose the most appropriate trajectory of management response. This approach allows not only to reduce the level of uncertainty but also to ensure effective alignment of strategic priorities with available resources, including legal, organizational, human and information resources³¹.

A special place in the overall system of national security management is occupied by strategic planning, which provides an opportunity to formulate strategic goals of the state security policy, develop mechanisms for implementing policies within specific regional contexts, and design alternative management strategies taking into account long-term risks and prospects. In particular, strategic planning serves as a tool for identifying and comprehensively substantiating potential threats that a region or the state as a whole may face, and also forms a management response in the form of a system of preventive, adaptive and crisis measures that can ensure the resilience of public administration to changes in the external environment³².

In addition, strategic planning plays a key role in ensuring the coherence of interests at the interlevel, such as between local communities, regional administrations and central executive authorities, which, in turn, contributes not only to the efficiency of the budget process and the effectiveness of the allocation of public resources, but also to the overall strengthening of the national security system in a limited resource and highly conflictual environment. At the same time, in the practice of public administration, there is a tendency to a flexible combination of strategic and tactical planning, depending on

³⁰ Meleouni, C., & Efthymiou, I. P. (2024). The Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in National Security: Defining International Standards and Guidelines. *Journal of Politics and Ethics in New Technologies and AI*, 3(1), e37847. <https://ejournals.epublishing.ekt.gr/index.php/jpentai/article/view/37847>

³¹ U.S. Department of Commerce. (2024). *The Decisive Decade: Advancing National Security at the Department of Commerce*. <https://www.commerce.gov/sites/default/files/2024-12/The-Decisive-Decade-Advancing-National-Security-at-the-Department-of-Commerce.pdf>

³² National Network of Safety and Security Analysts. (2024). *National Security Trend Analysis 2024: Accumulation of threats in times of uncertainty*. <https://www.rivm.nl/sites/default/files/2025-01/Dutch%20National%20Security%20Trend%20Analysis%202024-main%20report.pdf>

the level of emerging threats and the need to quickly adapt security policy to modern conditions, which confirms the importance of integrating planning approaches into the modern system of ensuring the national security of the country (Table 2).³³

Table 2. Functional aspects of public administration in ensuring the national security of the country

The function of public administration	The content of the public administration function in ensuring national security, taking into account organizational, legal, informational and personnel factors
Planning	Determination of strategic, tactical and operational goals in the field of national security, taking into account the specifics of regional development, including analysis of potential risks, modeling of security challenge scenarios and formation of a multi-level system of management decisions using information and analytical tools and engagement of qualified management personnel.
Organization	Formation of the institutional infrastructure of public administration of national security, which provides for a clear division of powers between central and regional authorities, creation of a regulatory framework for coordination of actions, provision of information support for management processes, as well as proper staffing in accordance with qualification requirements.
Motivation	Developing a system of administrative, legal and economic incentives for state and local government officials to increase the effectiveness of their participation in the implementation of national security policies, implementing partnership mechanisms with business and civil society, and encouraging initiatives aimed at increasing the resilience of regions to modern challenges.
Control	Conducting systematic monitoring of the state of national security using digital information processing tools, detecting critical deviations from normatively defined parameters, identifying new threats, as well as regularly evaluating the effectiveness of management actions and programs with subsequent adjustment of strategies based on feedback and up-to-date data.

Source: created by the author

³³ Ness, S., & Khinvasara, T. (2024). Emerging threats in cyberspace: Implications for national security policy and healthcare sector. *Journal of Engineering Research and Reports*, 26(2), 107–117. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jerr/2024/v26i21075>

In such conditions, the public administration activities of the state should ensure not only the timely mobilization of available resources, but also the deployment of adaptive management strategies that can maintain the sustainability of the financial, information and personnel subsystems of national security in the face of internal challenges and external threats.³⁴ The organizational function of public administration in the national security system plays an important role in the formation of a holistic and coordinated system of actions that ensures the availability, distribution and rational use of effective management resources, including material, financial and human resources, which are necessary for the implementation of the tasks of the state security policy at both the state and regional levels of government.

3. DISCUSSION

The results of the study demonstrate considerable consistency with existing scholarship in this area, while offering new perspectives for analysis. In particular, our findings confirm the views of Wiśniewski³⁵ on the systemic nature of national security and the need for integrated approaches to its management. There is also a similarity with the findings of Ahmed³⁶ (2024) and Slawotsky³⁷, who found that effective national security requires coordinated interaction of all branches of government through clearly defined organizational structures, legal regulation, and professional training. However, in contrast to Mahmutovic and Alhamoudi³⁸, who focus mainly on operational response, our paper provides a more comprehensive view, taking into account strategic planning and long-term adaptation of the security system. One of the key innovations of our study is the proposed model of integration of the three main subsystems of national security management: legal, institutional and instrumental. These results, in contrast to traditional verbal and logical methods of analysis³⁹, allow for a more detailed assessment of the interaction of different components of the security system and their impact on the overall effectiveness of governance. Especially important is the identification of weak links between different levels of governance, which is in line with the findings of Ryabets⁴⁰.

The contribution of the study to the scientific discourse is the development of specific mechanisms for reconciling the interests of different stakeholders through the system of stakeholder analysis. This toolkit, unlike those proposed earlier⁴¹, takes into account the specifics of the Ukrainian political system and the peculiarities of regional development. For practical application, it is important to develop a system of

³⁴ Nichev, N. (2017). Social security as part of the national security system of Bulgaria. *Security and Defense Quarterly*, 14(1), 3–20. <https://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0010.8467>

³⁵ Wiśniewski (2018). *Id.*

³⁶ Ahmed (2024). *Id.*

³⁷ Slawotsky (2024). *Id.*

³⁸ Mahmutovic & Alhamoudi (2023). *Id.*

³⁹ Metelenko et al. (2019). *Id.*

⁴⁰ Ryabets (2023). *Id.*

⁴¹ Mumtaz et al., (2024). *Id.*

forecasting and strategic planning, which, unlike existing models⁴², takes into account not only external threats but also internal challenges related to organizational, legal and personnel aspects of security management. This allows for more balanced and effective strategies to respond to potential threats. However, some of our findings contradict existing publications. In particular, in contrast to Lantis⁴³, who emphasizes the sufficiency of resources for national security, we found that the key factor is not so much the amount of resources as their effective allocation and use through clearly defined governance mechanisms. Also, our data does not fully support the views of Oerlemans and Langenhuijzen⁴⁴ on the priority of information technology in the national security system, as we found that the human and organizational components are equally important. In the context of the practical application of the research results, the proposed system of indicators and management mechanisms can be used to improve existing national security programs, which is relevant given the need to harmonize strategic documents at the national level with regional development plans, as emphasized by Weissmann⁴⁵.

Thus, the study not only confirms many existing theoretical positions, but also proposes new approaches to the analysis and management of national security, which greatly expands the possibilities for further research and practical application of the results.

CONCLUSION

4.

The study has established that an integrated model of public administration is needed to ensure national security in the context of increasing instability of the external environment. The model is aimed at strengthening the linkage of organizational, legal, information and personnel components as a single mechanism aimed at ensuring the sustainability and adaptability of public administration to rapidly changing threats and challenges. An important aspect is to take into account regional peculiarities and strategic development directions.

The author analyzes the main subsystems of the national security management system: legal, institutional and instrumental. Each of them performs specific functions: regulatory and legal regulation, coordination of activities of state structures, management of resources and information flows. Effective interaction of the subsystems is the key to successful implementation of the state security policy, building institutional strength and increasing trust in public administration.

The author proves the need for multi-level coordination between central, regional and local authorities in the process of strategic planning of national security. At the same time, it is important to take into account the interests of key stakeholders, such as

⁴² The Decisive Decade (2024). *Id.*

⁴³ Lantis (2002). *Id.*

⁴⁴ Oerlemans and Langenhuijzen (2024). *Id.*

⁴⁵ Weissmann (2025). *Id.*

the private sector, public organizations and the expert community. The concept of integrating strategic and operational planning into a single system with a clear division of tasks, identification of priority areas and mechanisms for responding to crisis situations has been formed. A comprehensive methodological toolkit for assessing the effectiveness of management mechanisms in the field of national security has been developed. It includes analysis of strategic documents, stakeholder assessment, comprehensive security assessment and multifactorial risk ranking. The proposed approach makes it possible to identify problem areas in the public administration system and develop reasonable recommendations for optimizing management decisions, taking into account current threats and limited human and information resources.

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